

The Satisfaction of Marriage to Men Who Have Been Divorced

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Abstract— Every human yearns for a harmonious household. Men in early adulthood who face tasks and stages of development begin to choose a life partner and build a family. Marriage satisfaction occurs because of the role of themselves and their partners in the marriage. When married, a person must be able to deal with changes in existing roles. If you are able to adjust and have the right partner, then the satisfaction of marriage will be achieved, but not all marriages end in what they expect. According to Hurlock (2002), divorce is the culmination of a poor marriage settlement, and what happens when a husband and wife are no longer able to find ways to resolve problems that can satisfy both parties. After a divorce many doubt that a man can survive alone, many factors that encourage men to get married again after a divorce in the hope of getting marriage satisfaction after divorce and re-marriage. This study aims to determine the satisfaction of marriage in men re-married after divorce. This research is qualitative research with case study design. Three respondents were taken using purposive sampling technique. Data collection uses interviews and observation. The results showed that marital satisfaction occurs due to the fulfilment of factors and aspects of marital satisfaction itself. From the results of the study, the third respondent experienced marital satisfaction because aspects of the satisfaction of the marriage were fulfilled. Unlike the first and second respondents who experienced dissatisfaction in their marriage. This is due to the non-fulfilment of aspects of marital satisfaction, including the absence of good two-way communication and the absence of efforts from respondents to improve relations.

Keywords— Divorced; Man; Marriage Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Early adulthood is a transition from adolescence to adulthood. Men in early adulthood are expected to play new roles such as the roles of husband, parent, breadwinner, and develop new attitudes, desires and values following their developmental tasks. According to Hurlock (2002), developmental tasks in early adulthood include starting work, choosing a life partner, starting to foster a family, caring for children, managing the household, taking responsibility as a citizen and looking for fun social groups.

Humans as individuals are social beings who have the desire to establish relationships with others. Humans were also created to live in pairs, to meet the needs that can only be met by having a partner. Marriage is something sacred that is built from a sacred bond. Marriage does not only unite a pair of lovers but also unites two families of different cultures and backgrounds. The differences that exist are not an obstacle to a marriage, on the contrary, the differences that exist are able to become the glue for them to complement and complement each other.

There is no marriage that wants to end with divorce. When the marriage has changed, the house will no longer be friendly. Some individuals will leave the marriage to seek peace. According to Hurlock (2002), divorce is the culmination of a poor marriage settlement, and what happens when a husband and wife are no longer able to find ways to resolve problems that can satisfy both parties, it is important to realize that many marriages do not produce happiness but do not end with divorce. According to George Levinger (in Lamanna, 2014), divorce generally occurs due to certain factors that encourage a husband and wife to divorce. These factors are the partner often ignores his obligations to the household and children, such as rarely returning home, lack of emotional closeness with children and spouse, insufficient financial problems for family needs, physical abuse of spouse, spouses often shout and issued harsh and hurtful words, no longer loyal, such as having another lover, mismatch in matters of sexual relations with her partner, such as often refusing and unable to provide satisfaction, the involvement or interference and social pressure from the partner's relatives, often arising suspicion, jealousy and mistrust of their partners, reduced feelings of love so they rarely communicate, lack of attention and togetherness between partners, the demands that are considered too excessive so a partner often becomes impatient, has no tolerance and feels too dominant in domestic life.

After a divorce, many doubted that a man would be able to survive alone for quite a long time. This is in line with the research of Tifani (2013) which explains that the fulfilment of variations in physiological needs of a widower includes eating, resting time, fulfilling sexual needs, the desire to remarry, and men who have divorced will generally get remarried. As a widower, the decision to remarry is strongly influenced by factors, first personal factors that concern the needs of a spouse, life during a wife has led to sharing experiences in various aspects of life. The second factor is social, often the environment (friends, neighbours, extended family) with their "glasses" assume that widowers (with children, if any) must have experienced many difficulties, and want to help. The last factor is the child, his perspective on child development or towards the child's feelings toward the new mother.

Habibi (2015) explains that marriage satisfaction occurs because of the fulfilment of aspects of marriage satisfaction itself. The possibility of men who have been divorced and remarried can get the satisfaction of marriage. Satisfaction can not be separated from meeting the needs expected by individuals. Satisfaction in marital relationships also affects

children, although in intact families children get fewer emotional and health problems and get better educational outcomes when the relationship between their parents is satisfying and relatively far from conflict (Karney & Crown, 2007).

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative approach to the type of case study research. In this study, taking respondents was done by purposive sampling technique. The characteristics of the respondents chosen were men who had divorced and remarried, aged between 21 and 40 years. The number of respondents is three people. The data collection technique is through interview and observation method.

III. RESULTS

The dominant cause of divorce among the three respondents was neglecting household obligations and being unfaithful to their spouse. Other causes such as financial problems, physical torture, spouses often yelled, mismatches in sexual relations, often drunk, there is no interference from spouse's relatives. However, the first and second respondent's divorce occurred because of the respondent's own behaviour.

The reasons for re-marriage among the three respondents were dominated by happiness, the support of family and friends, while other reasons included commitment factors such as wanting to have a pious woman and forgetting the past, relationship factors between partners such as wanting to give respect to a partner, friendship and sharing factors, for example, want to eliminate loneliness, want to have friends to exchange stories, the love factor, and the legitimacy factor of sex and child relations.

The factors that dominate marital satisfaction in men who have been divorced are the conditions of parental marriage happiness, the level of parental discipline, partner openness, mutual trust, equality between partners, freedom of communication in emotional, social and sexual. In the first and second respondents, almost every factor of marital satisfaction did not go well and there was always conflict and there was no good cooperation with a partner.

Overall aspects of the first and second respondent's marriage satisfaction did not go well such as communication that was not open, religious orientation was less than optimal, conflict resolution that did not produce a solution, financial management was not well coordinated, sexual orientation that concerned each other's satisfaction and was detrimental to partners, family and friend relationships are not harmonious, indifference to children and parenting, difficulty adjusting to marriage after divorce, lack of equality of role.

Based on indicators of marriage satisfaction of first and second respondents do not have cooperation in a relationship that is voluntary (friendship), do not consider marriage as a long-term commitment, something sacred, the lack of equality that the first and second respondents have with their partners, in married life, feelings positive is only felt one-sided, that is the only respondent, while wife feels unhappiness.

IV. DISCUSSION

Marriage is a strong bond based on feelings of love that are very deep from each party to live together to maintain human continuity on earth (Bachtia by both partners during the approach or dating will be realized in a marriage bond. As stated by Duvall and Miller (1985) define marriage as a relationship between men and women recognized in society that involves sexual relations, the existence of mastery and the right to care for children, and mutual understanding of their respective duties as husband and wife.

According to Hurlock (2002) states that divorce is a culmination of the poor marital settlement, and what happens when a husband and wife are no longer able to find ways to resolve problems that can satisfy both parties, it is important to realize that many marriages do not produce happiness but are not end with divorce.

George Levinger (in Lamanna, 2014) generally divorce occurs because of certain factors that encourage a husband and wife to divorce. The factors referred to between married couples are different from one another. Based on research conducted by George Levinger by taking a sample of 600 married couples who filed for divorce shows that complaints that are factors causing divorce are no responsibility towards the household, economic problems, often suspicious of the couple, domestic violence, shouting violently, unfaithfully, sex problems, lack of attention, and excessive demands.

According to Stinnett (in Turner & Helms, 1997), there are various reasons underlying why a person engages in marriage is a commitment, relationships between partners, friendship and sharing, love, happiness, the legitimacy of sexual relations and children.

Authority in marriage is an individual's subjective impression of the components of the marriage as a whole which includes love, togetherness, children, partner understanding, and the standard of living of Blood and Wolfe (in Santrock, 2007).

Bradbury, Fincham, and Beach (2000) say marital satisfaction is a reflection of the positive feelings felt by the couple more than the negative feelings towards their relationship so that marriage can continue to survive.

According to Duvall & Miller (1985), factors that influence one's marital satisfaction are happiness in parents' marriages, childhood happiness levels, levels of discipline that are not too high but are firm enough in giving penalties, there is adequate sex education from parents, minimum high school education or equivalent, and sufficient time to get acquainted with a partner before continuing to marriage: openness in expressing affection between husband and wife, mutual trust and confidence of both parties, equality between husband and wife, nothing dominates the parties others so that decisions are made together and there is openness, freedom in communicating between the two parties emotionally, socially and sexually.

According to Olson & Fowers (in Saragih 2003), there are several areas in a marriage that can be used to measure marital satisfaction. These areas include communication, leisure activities, religious orientation, conflict resolution, financial

management, sexual orientation, family and friends, children and parenting, personality problems, multiple roles.

Lauer and Lauer indicate marital satisfaction (in Baron & Byrne, 2003) into four indicators, which are positive feelings in living married life. These positive feelings are divided into three, namely: feeling a partner more attractive, feeling happiness with a partner, and feeling proud of a partner's achievement. Not only undergo mutual commitment, but the husband and wife must know their respective duties so that the marriage will go well because with marriage then all the expectations that are owned.

Marriage satisfaction occurs due to the fulfilment of factors and aspects in marriage satisfaction itself. From the results of the study, the third respondent experienced marriage satisfaction because aspects of the satisfaction of marriage have been fulfilled, but it is different from the first and second respondents who experiencing dissatisfaction in his marriage. This is due to the absence of good two-way communication and the absence of efforts from respondents to improve relations.

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